

The Reactions of the Cobaltic Ion-Part-II. The Kinetics of the Reaction of Cobaltic Ion with Some Dicarboxylic Saturated Acids*

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The kinetics of the oxidation of oxalic, malonic, and succinic acids with cobalt (III) in aqueous sulphuric acid have been studied for the first time. The rate of the reaction is of the first order with respect to both cobalt (III) and organic acids and shows an inverse acidity dependence upto 6*N* beyond which the rates tend to increase. For malonic and succinic acids there is a well defined short induction period, which is more for the latter compound. The rates have been found to be in the order,

Oxalic > malonic > succinic

The average values of the energies of activation are 25.25 k.cals. mole⁻¹, 26.60 k.cals mole⁻¹, and 31.20 k.cals mole⁻¹, respectively. The corresponding entropies of activation are +27.54 E.U., +25.55 E.U., and +34.12 E.U.

A possible mechanism is through the formation of intermediate complex of cobalt (III) with the undissociated organic acid, which then undergoes fragmentation and is the rate determining step.

A survey of literature reveals that the kinetic studies of the oxidation of oxalic acid and its homologues have not been conducted with cobalt (III) in aqueous sulphuric acid. In this paper the results of the kinetic studies of the oxidation of oxalic, malonic, and succinic acids by cobalt (III) produced *in situ* by the interaction of potassium cobalt (III) carbonate and sulphuric acid, have been presented.

EXPERIMENTAL

Freshly prepared solutions of cobalt (III) generated *in situ* by the interaction of potassium cobalt (III) carbonate¹ and sulphuric acid were used. All the reagents used were of A.R. or equivalent grade. The standard solutions were prepared by usual methods. The kinetics of the reaction was followed for the interacting mixture in a temperature bath maintained at desired temperature within $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The mixtures contained large excesses of organic compounds and loss of the oxidant was estimated iodometrically.

The order of reaction with respect to cobalt (III) was determined by applying rate equations for first and second order reactions and finding out as to which equation could be satisfactorily applied. Then the order with respect to organic compound was determined by the relation :

$$n = \frac{\log K_1/K_1'}{\log C_1/C_1'}$$

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1. Part I, Sthapak and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970 (in Press).

where K_1 and K_1' are calculated rate constants obtained from the loss of cobalt (III) corresponding to reductant concentrations C_1 and C_2 of the organic compound, respectively. The total order of the reaction was then obtained by adding the two. In all the cases, experiments were run in duplicate and the results were found to be reproducible with the maximum variation of the constants being $\pm 5\%$.

1. *Effect of Oxalic acid on the rate of the reduction of cobalt (III) in aqueous sulphuric acid*: The average values of first order rate constants for the loss of cobalt (III) in presence of 9.75N sulphuric acid, at three temperatures have been recorded below:—

TABLE IA

Cobalt (III) initial = $1.25 \times 10^{-3}M$. $H_2SO_4 = 9.75 N$. K-Salts of $H_2SO_4 = 0.25N$.

No.	Oxalic acid concentrations $\times 10^{-3}M$	Average first-order rate constants $\times 10^3 \text{min}^{-1}$		
		(at $0^\circ C \pm 0.1$)	(at $5^\circ C \pm 0.1$)	(at $10^\circ C \pm 0.1$)
1.	3.125	13.61	27.80	65.17
2.	4.15	16.74	39.61	89.54
3.	6.25	24.13	53.77	—
4.	8.30	29.08	71.51	—
5.	12.50	42.12	98.10	—
6.	16.60	56.15	—	—

From the above table it may therefore, be concluded that order of the reaction with respect to both cobalt (III) and oxalic acid is one. Hence, total order of the reaction is two.

Effect of Sulphuric acid on the rate of oxidation of Oxalic acid by cobalt (III): Different concentrations of sulphuric acid were used. The quantities of potassium bicarbonate present in excess in the complex and potassium cobalt (III) carbonate reacting with sulphuric acid to form its potassium salts have been calculated. In the following tables the average values of first order constants, for the loss of cobalt (III) in presence of different concentrations of sulphuric acid left over in excess, are given:

TABLE IB

Cobalt (III) initial = $1.25 \times 10^{-3}M$. Temperature = $0^\circ C \pm 0.1$. K-Salts of $H_2SO_4 = 0.25N$

No.	Sulphuric Acid concentrations (N)	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{min}^{-1}$	
		Oxalic Acid Concentrations	
		($6.25 \times 10^{-3}M$)	($8.33 \times 10^{-3}M$)
1.	2.25	63.10	83.66
2.	3.75	31.53	43.62
3.	4.75	25.90	34.08
4.	6.75	21.42	24.66
5.	9.75	23.84	29.08
6.	11.25	28.83	38.71

From the above table it is clear that with increasing concentration of sulphuric acid, rate of the reaction first decreases. However, after certain concentration of the mineral acid, it tends to increase.

(II) *Effect of Malonic Acid on the rate of Reduction of Cobalt (III) in aqueous sulphuric acid*: In the following table the average values of first order constants for the loss of cobalt (III) in presence of 9.75*N* sulphuric acid and at three temperatures have been presented.

TABLE IIA

Cobalt (III) initial = $1.25 \times 10^{-3} M$. K-salts of $H_2SO_4 = 0.25 N$. $H_2SO_4 = 9.75 N$.

No.	Malonic Acid concentrations $\times 10^{-3} M$	Average first-order rate constants $\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$		
		($10^\circ C \pm 0.1$)	($15^\circ C \pm 0.1$)	($20^\circ C \pm 0.1$)
1.	3.125	—	3.80	9.85
2.	6.25	2.92	6.91	17.41
3.	12.50	6.19	12.60	30.30
4.	25.00	12.62	24.13	55.96
5.	50.00	27.63	53.89	132.84
6.	100.00	67.71	—	—

A perusal of the above table clearly shows that, order of the reaction is one with respect to both cobalt (III) and malonic acid. The total order is, therefore, two. Again at lower concentrations of sulphuric acid or at lower temperatures a short but well-defined induction period has also been observed.

Effect of Sulphuric acid on the Rate of Oxidation of Malonic Acid by Cobalt (III): In the following table, the effect of different concentrations of sulphuric acid on the rate of oxidation of malonic acid by cobalt (III) has been summarised.

TABLE IIB

Cobalt (III) = $1.25 \times 10^{-3} M$. Temperature = $10^\circ C \pm 0.1$. K-Salts of $H_2SO_4 = 0.25 N$

No.	Sulphuric acid concentrations (<i>N</i>)	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	
		Malonic acid concentrations	
		($1.25 \times 10^{-2} M$)	($2.50 \times 10^{-2} M$)
1.	4.75	6.65	13.82
2.	5.75	5.18	10.64
3.	6.75	4.84	9.92
4.	9.75	6.19	12.62

From the above table it may be concluded that the effect of sulphuric acid on the rate of oxidation of malonic acid by cobalt (III) is similar to that, observed for the reaction between cobalt (III) and oxalic acid,

(III) *Effect of Succinic acid on the rate of Reduction of Cobalt (III) in aqueous sulphuric acid*: The effect of different concentrations of succinic acid on the rate of reduction of cobalt (III) in 9.75*N* sulphuric acid at three temperatures has been recorded below:

TABLE IIIA

Cobalt (III) initial = $1.25 \times 10^{-3} M$. K-Salts of $H_2SO_4 = 0.25 N$. $H_2SO_4 = 9.75 N$.

No.	Succinic Acid concentration $\times 10^{-2} N$	Average first order rate constants $\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$		
		(25°C \pm 0.1)	(30°C \pm 0.1)	(35°C \pm 0.1)
1.	2.50	5.41	14.09	31.00
2.	3.125	6.19	20.22	36.09
3.	5.00	9.53	23.88	53.20
4.	6.25	11.28	31.32	60.25
5.	12.50	22.13	47.12	106.12

It may be concluded, therefore, that order of the reaction with respect to succinic acid is slightly less than one. Hence, the total order of the reaction is two.

Effect of Sulphuric acid on the rate of Oxidation of Succinic acid by Cobalt (III): The effect of different concentrations of sulphuric acid on the rate of oxidation of succinic acid by cobalt (III) has been summarised in the following table:

TABLE IIIB

Cobalt (III) initial = $1.25 \times 10^{-3} M$. Temperature = 35°C \pm 0.1. K-Salts of $H_2SO_4 = 0.25 N$

No.	Sulphuric acid concentration (<i>N</i>)	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	
		Succinic acid concentrations	
		($3.125 \times 10^{-2} M$)	($6.25 \times 10^{-2} M$)
1.	7.75	25.12	51.63
2.	8.75	30.10	53.80
3.	9.75	36.16	60.25

It is, therefore, clear that the rate of reaction between cobalt (III) and succinic acid increases with the increasing concentration of sulphuric acid (beyond 7*N*).

Note: In all the kinetic studies of the oxidation of organic compounds it has been necessary to use such concentrations of sulphuric acid as may effectively suppress the reaction of cobalt (III) with water. At these concentrations of the mineral acid, the dissociation of organic acids (reported in this paper) is more or less completely suppressed². The depressing effect of sulphuric acid, which is apparent in its lower concentration range could not, therefore, be observed here.

Effect of Temperature: The reactions have been studied at different temperatures and the values of the temperature-coefficient, energy of activation, frequency-factor and

2. Bell, "The Proton in Chemistry", Methuen, London, 1960.

the entropy of activation have been calculated by the usual method. The average values have been presented in the following table :

TABLE IV

No.	Compound	Temperature	Temperature coefficient	Energy of activation k.cals mole ⁻¹	Frequency factor litres mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	Entropy of activation (E.U.)
1.	Oxalic Acid	10–0°C	5.06	24.90	10.42 × 10 ¹⁸	+27.54
2.	Malonic Acid	20–10°C	5.02	26.75	3.84 × 10 ¹⁸	+25.55
3.	Succinic Acid	35–25°C	5.56	31.28	2.87 × 10 ²⁰	+34.12

DISCUSSION

Cobalt (III) ions are known to be solvated and water molecules fill the coordination sphere around the metal atoms. It has been suggested that an equilibrium of the following type 3, 4, 5 is rapidly set up

It is also known that the hexa-coordinated cobalt (III) ion is fairly inert⁶ for substitution and that, in the presence of (SO₄²⁻) ions, one or two water molecules in pentaquo cobalt (III) ions are replaced by (SO₄²⁻), and the corresponding coordinated complexes^{4,7} are formed.

It has been noted that cobalt (III) added in the form of potassium cobalt (III) oxalate does not appreciably induce the reactivity of an oxalate-oxalic acid mixture towards its reaction with either potassium permanganate or mercuric chloride but the same can be achieved by adding and neutralizing the bicarbonate present in the cobalt (III) complex. It appears, therefore, that the reaction :

is not a rapid process. If the acidity is however increased, C₂O₄²⁻ are changed to HC₂O₄⁻ or even to undissociated H₂C₂O₄, which may substitute water molecules in the pentaquo-cobalt (III) ion. The product so formed appears to be more unstable and capable to decompose, resulting in the oxidation of oxalic acid and simultaneous reduction of cobalt (III). Thus

3. Hoare and Waters, *ibid.*, 1962, 965; 1964, 2552.
4. Sutcliffe and Weber, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1955, **51**, 786; *ibid.*, 1961, **57**, 91.
5. Shanker and De Souza, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1962, **24**, 693.
6. Friedman, Taube and Hunt, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1950, **18**, 759.
7. Ashurst and Higginson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 343.

The radical $\dot{\text{H}}\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ so generated reacts with the free or coordinated cobalt (III) ion to give the final oxidation products :

As the reaction is of the first order with respect to both cobalt (III) and oxalic acid, it appears that the step (2) is slow and rate determining. The depressing effect of hydrogen ions is clearly understood from relations (2) and (3). The results also point out that as the concentration of sulphuric acid is continuously increased, the rate slows down and after passing through a minimum it increases. It is, therefore, possible that under such circumstances because of the high concentration of sulphuric acid as compared to the organic acid cobalt (III) sulphate complexes are formed. This brings about a change in the very nature of the reaction and under these circumstances a direct interaction of cobalt (III) sulphate complex with these organic acids may take place. Similar mechanism can be extended to explain the reaction between cobalt (III) and malonic or succinic acid. Hence, the general rate expression that will hold good for the reaction between cobalt (III), and these acids in moderate concentrations of sulphuric acid may be written as :

$$-\frac{d[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}]}{dt} = k[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}][\text{Organic acid}]/[\text{H}^+]$$

Let us now discuss for the existence of a well defined short induction period for malonic and succinic acids. It is known that potassium cobalt (III) oxalate^{8,9} is readily formed but the formation of potassium cobalt (III) malonate is a slow process and the cobalt (III) complex of potassium succinate has not been isolated. The replacement of water molecules in the aquo cobalt (III) ion by malonic or succinic acid is, therefore, slow. This will account for a short induction period noted during the oxidation of these two acids. A short induction period for the reaction of cobalt (III) with methyl alcohol has also been reported by Bawn and White¹⁰ and it appears that the substitution of methyl alcohol for the water molecules associated with cobalt (III) is also a slow process.

The values of energy of activation and frequency factor for these reactions are unusually high. This may be ascribed to the significant influence of temperature on the formation of different species of cobalt (III) taking part in these reactions. It may also be concluded that the reduction of cobaltic ion, though it involves one electron transfer, is not a simple process and operative mechanisms vary under different experimental conditions.

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8. Thomas, *Chem. Soc. Trans.*, 1921, **119**, 1140.
9. Sharp and White, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 110.
10. Bawn and White, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 331.